

Atmospheric Dispersion Corrector: from design phase to on-sky commissioning

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Astronomical observations with ground-based telescopes are affected by differential atmospheric dispersion, a consequence of the wavelength-dependent index of refraction of the atmosphere. The problem of atmospheric dispersion is particularly serious for high-resolution spectrographs aiming at sub-pixel radial velocity (RV) precision. In order to detect Earth-like planets orbiting Sun-like stars, an RV precision of around 10 cm s^{-1} must be achieved. With the objective of developing high-resolution spectrographs that can reach such a RV precision [1], a correction of atmospheric dispersion variation down to this level of positioning accuracy must be included. An Atmospheric Dispersion Corrector (ADC) is thus mandatory [2].

What is an ADC?

An ADC, is a prism, or a set of prisms, that is used to counteract the effect of atmospheric dispersion. As we know, a prism produces refraction. An ADC is supposed to produce an equal amount of dispersion as the atmosphere, and in an opposite direction. The design of an ADC can vary from a simple prism, to a complicated counter-rotating prism made of two or more prisms glued together. One of the most common types of ADC, is the rotating atmospheric dispersion corrector. The ADC can perform two rotations: i) when the two prisms rotate together to define the ADC dispersion direction that should oppose that of the sky; ii) when the two prisms counter-rotate to define the ADC dispersion amount that should be equal to that of the sky (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Left: schematic of a rotating ADC; right: schema of the different rotations of an ADC.

How can we design/model an ADC?

As mentioned before, an ADC is supposed to create a dispersion with an equal amount, and opposite direction to that of the sky in order to cancel it. The design of an ADC is usually based on atmospheric dispersion models, that up to our knowledge, were never tested on-sky. With the increase of the requirements demands on the ADC, with residuals at the level of few tens of milli-arcseconds (mas), it is important to re-visit how an ADC is modeled.

For example, the difference between the two most common models, Filippenko [3] and Zemax [4], is higher than the required residuals. Therefore we developed a method to measure on-sky the atmospheric dispersion to better characterize the different models [5, 6].

The method is based on the use of cross-dispersion spectrographs to determine the position of the centroid of the spatial profile at each wavelength of each spectral order. The method is validated using cross-dispersed spectroscopic data acquired with the slit spectrograph UVES. The accuracy of the method is 18 mas. At this level, we are able to compare and characterize the different atmospheric dispersion models of interest. For better future ADC designs, we recommend to avoid the Zemax model, and in particular in the blue range of the spectra, when expecting residuals at the level of few tens of mas.

Figure 2: Top: expected RV error due to ADC residuals; bottom: expected flux losses at 380 nm due to ADC residuals.

How can we define ADC residuals requirements?

When designing an ADC, an important factor that plays a role is the requirement set, in particular the ADC residuals (remaining dispersion after sky correction). These residuals errors can affect the position of the target as perceived on the sky and its flux distribution. This effect will affect the results of astronomical observations. Therefore, it was important that we test the effect of atmospheric dispersion on astronomical observations in general, and in particular on RV precision degradation and flux losses. Our scientific objective is to quantify the amount of residuals needed to fulfil the requirements set on an ADC during the design phase [7]. We found that up to a dispersion of 100 mas, the effect on the RV is negligible. However, on the flux losses, such a dispersion

can create a loss of $\sim 2\%$ at 380 nm, a significant value when efficiency is critical. The requirements set on ADC residuals should take into consideration the atmospheric conditions where the ADC will function, and also all the aspects related with not only the RV precision requirements but also the guiding camera used, the tolerances on the flux loss, and the different melt data of the chosen glasses. Figure 2 summarise the relation between ADC residuals and RV errors as well as flux losses.

How can we validate an ADC on-sky?

Another important step in the lifetime of an ADC, after setting its requirements and designing it, is to be able to validate it on-sky. As mentioned before, the rotating ADC can perform two rotations, that should be perfectly aligned with the sky dispersion. Insufficient or wrong correction of the atmospheric dispersion produces a spectrally elongated shape instead of a circular white one for the observed target. The commissioning tests of ADCs with on-sky observations are not an easy task. In fact, the residual dispersion is expected to be of a few tens of mas, with the object for a seeing limited telescope being almost 1 arcsec. A procedure was developed [8], based on ellipse fitting of several cuts from the guiding camera

images, to determine the levels of oblongness in an object image caused by atmospheric dispersion. The characterisation of the data allows for the validation of the ADC alignment by determining the dispersion direction and minimizing the ellipticity. The procedure was tested and demonstrated using simulated data that mimics the expected images using real sky dispersion models and real sensor characteristics. The accuracy of the method is highly dependent on the observational conditions and on the ratio between expected elongation (dispersion) and image size, but it is expected that the method can be more sensitive than traditional ADC on-sky alignment methods.

References

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